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Assessing the Effectiveness and Feasibility of the Experienced Carers Helping Others (ECHO) Program in Relatives of Adolescents with Eating Disorders Using an Online Application Format with Individual Sessions

Abstract

Eating disorders (ED) usually involve hospital admission and a high relapse rate, with the return home being a critical moment for patients and their families. After their return home, they often have trouble incorporating the guidelines they have learned into their daily context. ECHOMANTRA intervention program aims to facilitate this transition by offering psychological strategies that involve both patients and their families and carers. Specifically, the ECHO program is aimed at the relatives of these patients. The present study aimed to analyse the efficacy of adding the ECHO program to the usual treatment (TAU) of relatives through a novel format based on individual intervention and with an online format, and to examine the acceptability and feasibility of this new format. The study design was multi-center, randomised, controlled, with a longitudinal design and comparing two parallel groups. A total of 108 family members participated. Results indicated that relatives from both groups, TAU and ECHO+TAU, showed improvements in expressed emotion, accommodation, impact of the ED, emotional wellbeing and caregiver skills. However, effect sizes in the ECHO+TAU group were slightly larger than the TAU group. In addition, the changes were greater in depression and caregiver skills when the ECHO component was added. Most caregivers (81.48%) completed the ECHO and indicated a high level of satisfaction with the program. These results suggest the efficacy and the feasibility of adding the ECHO intervention program to the usual treatment in an individual online format.

Keywords: Experienced Carers Helping Others; ECHO; Eating disorders; Carers; RCT

Assessing the Effectiveness and Feasibility of the Experienced Carers Helping Others (ECHO) Program in Relatives of Adolescents with Eating Disorders Using an Online Application Format with Individual Sessions

Eating disorders (ED) are severe mental illnesses, typically developing in adolescence, characterised by the severity of their symptoms and their high mortality and comorbidity (Arcelus et al., 2011; Fitcher & Quadflieg, 2016). In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of cases, as well as in their severity, with a 104% increase in children and adolescents with EDs requiring hospital admissions (Santomauro et al., 2021). When patients require intensive treatment, they are addressed through hospital admissions or specialised day centres. However, there is a high rate of relapses and readmissions, especially after treatment has ended (Berends et al., 2018), highlighting the need for support in the transition to the community through specialised psychological interventions (Bryan et al., 2021). In this regard, interventions that promote social support during recovery are considered particularly beneficial, given that difficulties in interpersonal relationships may contribute to increased ED symptoms (Treasure et al., 2020).

In response to this, Dr. Janet Treasure's team developed the ECHOMANTRA intervention program, which aims to facilitate the transition from inpatient treatment to daily life in one's community (Adamson et al., 2019; Cardi et al., 2017). This program is based on scientific evidence that family involvement in the treatment of EDs is a key strategy for recovery (Levine, 2012, Treasure & Nazar, 2016; Sepúlveda et al., 2020). ECHOMANTRA is composed of the ECHO program for caregivers (*ECHO; Experienced Carers Helping Others*; Treasure et al., 2015) and MANTRA for patients (MANTRA; Schmidt et al., 2014). The MANTRA program is based on the Cognitive

Maintenance Model of Anorexia Nervosa (Schmidt et al., 2014) which synthesizes the main internal and external maintenance factors of the disorder, emphasising behavioural change strategies and focusing on steps for successful transition from hospital admission to daily life.

The ECHO program, aimed at family members, builds on the importance of interpersonal relationships in the maintenance of ED (Treasure et al., 2021) and provides assistance and training to caregivers in handling this role. Recovery from ED can involve many years of treatment (NICE, 2017), during which time the patient may require a significant degree of family (Adamson et al., 2019) and healthcare support (Hibbs et al., 2015). During the recovery process, families may experience high levels of emotional, familial and/or financial strain (Fernández-Aranda et al., 2021). Two systematic reviews have shown that the problems associated with this illness negatively impact the quality of life for all family members leading to burden, distress, accommodating and enabling behaviours and expressed emotion (Anastasiadou et al., 2014; Zabala et al., 2009). Family members often request information and help with the caregiver role (Hibbs et al., 2015). For this reason, including family in treatment is a recommendation from main clinical guides (Couturier et al., 2020; National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), 2017). Involving the family during in-patient care for adults as well as children can have benefits for both the patient and the caregiver (Hibbs et al., 2015).

Studies have shown that the ECHO program improves caregivers' levels of well-being, and reduces psychological distress and expressed emotion (Magill et al., 2016; Hodsoll et al., 2017). Furthermore, patients whose caregivers participated in these groups also reduced their anxiety, depression, and psychological distress scores (Hibbs et al., 2015; Pepin & King, 2013; Sepulveda et al., 2008; 2009; Treasure & Nazar,

2016). This program, adapted to a Spanish population by the authors, led to improved levels of anxiety, depression, and psychological distress among *carers*. There was also a reduction in symptom accommodation behaviours, and an increase in the perception of control over how ED affected their lives. Furthermore, patients whose family members participated in these groups experienced decreased levels of anxiety, depression and psychological distress (Pérez-Pareja et al., 2015; Quiles et al., 2018). Another study, in which ECHO was implemented as a novel transition support intervention in an adult ED service, reported a moderate reduction in carer burden, a small/moderate increase in carers skills, and an increase in efficacy at reducing anorexia nervosa behaviours. However, levels of distress were mostly unchanged and there was little impact on reducing accommodating and enabling behaviours (Adamson et al., 2019). A recent review study concluded that ECHO can also reduce service costs by reducing relapse and readmission rates in specialised centres (Treasure et al., 2020).

The ECHO program has been designed to be affordable, scalable and have a potentially wide reach (Cardi et al., 2015), making its application increasingly accessible. Previous research showed interest in using digital approaches to improve treatments for transition programs (Cardi et al., 2017; Fitcher et al., 2012). A recent meta-analysis recommends, given the clinical and economic success of the ECHO program, adapting it to digital/ online features that allow it to be applied remotely (Hanna et al., 2022). Another novel contribution of the present work is its application to carers of adolescent patients. Until now, studies have primarily focused on adult patients. Therefore, the aim of this paper was to evaluate the efficacy of adding the ECHO program to the usual treatment (TAU) of relatives through a novel format based on individual intervention and with an online format. Additionally, we aimed to evaluate the acceptability and feasibility of this new approach. This trial investigated the

following hypothesis: The primary hypothesis (a) was that carers allocated to ECHO+TAU would present improved psychological well-being and lower levels of illness accommodation, expressed emotion, and burden in comparison to carers from the control group (TA). The second hypothesis (b) was that carers from the experimental group would have more ED carer skills in comparison to carers from the control group. Finally, the third hypothesis (c) was that the efficacy of the combined intervention (ECHO+TAU) would remain stable in the 3-, 6- and 12- month follow-up.

Method

The protocol paper provides further details and information about methodology (Quiles et al., 2021). This study has been registered on the ISRCTN registry (Trial Identifier: ISRCTN43554732).

Participants

Family participants ($N = 108$) comprised 92 women (85.2%) and 16 men (14.8) (age range: 30-64, $M = 48.43$, $SD = 5.26$) were recruited from seven different specialist inpatient/day-patient/outpatient eating disorder units spread throughout Spain. To be eligible for this study the carers had to be currently living with the patient and had to be a primary carer (somebody who usually takes care of the patient outside the hospital/day-center and lives with them), be able to access and manage an electronic device (e.g., mobile phone, computer, laptop or tablet) and the Internet in order to access online sessions, and to be a native Spanish speaker or understand Spanish at a native level. Carers were excluded from the study if they were suffering from a serious medical or psychiatric condition and if their daughter declined to participate in the study. Both parents were invited to participate in the study, and in the case that they were assigned to the experimental group, both could receive the ECHO program

sessions. However, only the data from one of them was considered for the data analyses, usually the one who attended the sessions more frequently.

Respect patients, and following the same guidelines as the original ECHOMANTRA study (Cardi et al., 2017), only women with an ED participated in this study. In addition, it is important to note that the MANTRA program was designed to apply to women. Therefore, patients were included if they were women with an eating disorder diagnosis according to the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), were aged between 12-19, had no psychiatric comorbidity, were receiving treatment for ED in a specialist inpatient/day-patient/outpatient ED unit, had the ability to manage an electronic device and the Internet to access online sessions, and were native Spanish speakers or understood Spanish at a native level. This information was assessed through a self-report and provided by the psychologist and/or the psychiatrists who attended to them in their eating disorder unit. Patients were asked to nominate a carer to whom the researcher invited to participate in the study.

Instruments

Clinical and socio-demographic data.

Carers completed a *sociodemographic questionnaire ad-hoc* that included age, gender, marital status, educational and employment status. Clinical data of the patients was completed by the health care providers at the unit and included: diagnosis, illness duration, and care level.

Emotional wellbeing.

It was evaluated with *Depression and Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21)*; Bados et al., 2005; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995). The instrument consists of 21 items divided into three subscales that assess the emotional state: depression, anxiety, and stress. The scoring of each item ranges from 0 (*did not apply to me at all*) to 3 (*applied to me very*

much or most of the time), scores are the addition of the items, and range from 0 to 63.

Higher scores indicate a poorer emotional state. The instrument shows adequate internal consistency ranging from $\alpha \geq .70$ to $\alpha \geq .84$ in the Spanish validation study. Specifically, the reliability estimates for the present sample ranged from $\alpha \geq .79$ to $\alpha \geq .87$ in the subscales, and $\alpha \geq .92$ in the global score.

Expressed emotion.

Be assessed with *Family Questionnaire (FQ)*; Sepúlveda et al., 2014; Wiedemann et al., 2002). The instrument consists of 20 items distributed across two scales: critical comments (CC, 10 items) and emotional over-involvement (EOI, 10 items). The scoring of each item ranges from 1 (*never/rarely*) to 4 (*very often*), scores are the addition of the items, and range from 20 to 80. Higher scores indicate greater expressed emotion. The instrument shows adequate psychometric properties in the Spanish validation study ($\alpha \geq .83$, $\alpha \geq .72$, respectively in each subscale). The reliability estimates for the present sample were $\alpha \geq .71$ and $\alpha \geq .83$, respectively in each subscale, and $\alpha \geq .86$ in the global score.

Caregiving burden.

The assessment of the degree of impact of the ED on the caregiver was carried out using the *Eating Disorders Symptom Impact Scale (EDSIS-S)*; Carral-Fernández et al., 2013; Sepúlveda et al., 2008). The instrument consists of 24 items distributed into four scales: nutrition impact, guilt, dysregulated behaviors and social isolation. The scoring on each item ranges from 0 (*never*) to 4 (*nearly always*), scores are the addition of the items, and range from 0 to 96. Higher scores indicate a greater impact of the ED upon the caregiver over the previous month. The Spanish validation of the instrument shows adequate internal consistency ranging from $\alpha \geq .74$ to $\alpha \geq .83$ in the dimensions, and $\alpha \geq .88$ for

the total scale. The reliability estimates for the present sample ranged from $\alpha \geq .65$ to $\alpha \geq .85$, respectively in each subscale, and $\alpha \geq .85$ in the global score.

Illness accommodation.

To assess this domain, we use the *Accommodation to Illness Symptoms Scale (AESED)*; Quiles et al., 2016; Sepúlveda et al., 2009). The instrument consists of 33 items distributed across five subscales: avoidance and modifying routine, reassurance seeking, meal ritual, control of family and 'turning a blind eye'. Participants rate each item using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 0 (*never*) to 4 (*nearly always*), scores are the addition of the items, and range from 0 to 132. Higher scores indicate a greater degree of family accommodation to the illness. The instrument shows adequate internal consistency ranging from $\alpha \geq .74$ to $\alpha \geq .89$ in the Spanish validation study. The reliability estimates for the present sample ranged from $\alpha \geq .71$ to $\alpha \geq .85$, respectively in each subscale, and $\alpha \geq .91$ in the global score.

Caregiver Skills.

These skills were measured through the *Caregiver Skills Scale (CASK)* (Vintró-Alcaraz et al., 2018; Hibbs et al., 2015). The instrument consists of 27 items distributed into six subscales: bigger picture, self-care, biting-your-tongue, insight-acceptance, emotional intelligence and frustration-tolerance, scored on a visual analogue scale anchored from 0 to 100. Scores are the mean of the items. Higher scores reflect increased caregiver skills that can benefit patients with eating disorders. In the Spanish validation study the instrument shows adequate psychometric properties ranging from $\alpha \geq .71$ to $\alpha \geq .75$. The reliability estimates for the present sample ranged from $\alpha \geq .60$ to $\alpha \geq .72$, respectively in each subscale, and $\alpha \geq .87$ in the global score.

Acceptability and feasibility of the ECHO.

Carers in the ECHO arm completed a “Participant Feedback Form.”, created ad hoc for completion at the end of the intervention. It consisted of 12 likert-type items (e.g., Do you think the sessions have been useful to improve your experience as a caregiver?), ranging from 1 (*nothing at all*) to 10 (*very much*), and assessed participants’ experiences and satisfaction with the study. They were asked to provide their views regarding: what they found beneficial and/or challenging, what they enjoyed and/or did not like, the transferability of ECHO skills to their routine, and their suggestions for further improvements to the intervention. In addition, the session facilitator documented session attendance, task compliance between sessions, and reading material completion for each session.

Procedure

Design

This study used a multi-center, randomized, controlled, double-masked design comparing two parallel groups, following CONSORT guidelines. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the different hospitals to which the eating disorders units belonged and the Ethics Committee of the University Miguel Hernández.

Prior to the conduct of this study, patients had already been diagnosed by the corresponding clinician staff in their respective units. The research assistant at each center, commonly clinical psychologists or psychiatrists from the participating units, evaluated carers and participants’ fulfillment of the inclusion criteria and provided detailed information on the study. Patients and carers who were willing to participate, were requested written informed consent and the completion of the baseline questionnaires by the research assistant at their unit. Once completed, participants were randomly assigned into two groups: receiving Treatment as Usual (TAU) only or receiving the ECHO MANTRA intervention complementary to TAU. A research

administrator independent of the clinicians involved in the assessment and in the treatment used a computer-generated randomized sequence, with 1:1 treatment allocation.

This study employed a longitudinal RCT design and 12 month follow-ups. Carers completed self-report questionnaires provided by the research assistant at their corresponding unit just before the start of the intervention at baseline (T0). Once the study intervention concluded, the clinicians involved administered a self-report questionnaire to the carers who participated (two months apart from the baseline) (T1) and carried out follow-ups by periodically contacting at 3 months (T2), 6 months (T3) and 12 months (T4) after the completion of the intervention. As the patients also received an intervention, they had to complete the battery of questions at the same time intervals as the carers were assessed. Nonetheless, in this study we only present the data and results corresponding to family members.

One hundred-eight carers agreed to participate: 54 were allocated to the TAU-only group and 54 to the ECHO group. Questionnaire completion rates were, for TAU-only: 92.45% in T1, 84.90% in T2, 79.25% in T3 and 75.47% in T4; and for ECHO+TAU: 81.48% in T1, 74.07% in T2, 68.51% in T3 and 66.67% in T4.

Figure 1 shows the CONSORT diagram for the study.

INSERT FIGURE 1

Interventions

Treatment as Usual (TAU)

We did not use a standardized comparison treatment as this would require practical changes in different settings which was not feasible. Each center followed their own procedures for TAU, which can be considered standard practice in Spain. It is expected that the eating disorders units, which belong to the public health services in

Spain, follow the recommendations of the Clinical Practice Guidelines of the National Health System (NHS), which indicates that it is important to get the support and involvement of the family, help them to cope with the situation and raise awareness so that they adopt positive changes in their family routine. TAU should also include information and advice. This information aims to enhance understanding of the disease, its origin, consequences and treatments.

The 24-hour hospitalization services that have participated in this study (Hospital Universitario La Fe in Valencia, Reina Sofia in Murcia and San Juan in Alicante) offer a program with a multidisciplinary team approach (nutritionist/endocrinologist, psychologist, physician and nurse). It includes monitoring of physical risks, nutritional rehabilitation, education on healthy eating and nutrition guidelines. In addition, work is done to try to modify/improve the thoughts, attitudes, behaviors and feelings that maintain the disease through psychological therapy. Once the patient has stabilized and reached a healthy body mass index, the patient is discharged. She is then followed up to assess her progress and evaluate whether she should continue her treatment in another resource (outpatient unit/day hospital). The usual treatment in the day hospitals of CREA (Centro de Recuperación Emocional y Alimentaria), ADANER (Asociación en Defensa de la Atención a la Anorexia Nerviosa y Bulimia) and the Hospital de La Fé in Valencia, enables continuous care and a progressive transition from inpatient to outpatient care. Interdisciplinary treatment is carried out including dietary support/therapeutic feeding, psychological interventions and school support. Patients receive the following psychological interventions: weekly individual cognitive-behavioral therapy for eating disorders (CBT-ED); and psychoeducational group therapy on nutrition, emotion management, body image, social skills and problem-solving strategies. Patients usually attend every weekday (Monday

through Friday) for an average of 6 hours per day. Parents can also access psycho-educational groups that are held on a twice-monthly for support.

The usual treatment in the Outpatient Units of the Hospital de la Fé and the CREA center involves psychological interventions to modify/improve the thoughts, attitudes, behaviors and feelings that maintain the disease. They offer nutritional and medical support when needed.

The TAU condition did not have access to intervention materials or ECHOMANTRA intervention sessions.

Treatment as Usual Plus Carer Skill-Sharing Intervention (ECHO+TAU)

The original ECHO program was delivered in the form of workshops that aimed to reduce carer distress (Sepúlveda et al., 2008). As a next step, the training materials were synthesised into a self-help intervention with a book and a set of DVDs to facilitate dissemination and careers access. Research showed that it was a feasible and acceptable intervention (Goodard et al., 2011). In the present RCT, sessions are delivered individually and online, allowing it to be tailored to the personal circumstances of families, with greater adherence to the programme (Quiles et al., 2021).

Carer's intervention (ECHO) consisted of a total of eight weekly, individual online sessions, lasting 60 min each, which were delivered by assistant psychologists trained in the ECHO intervention and supervised by the principal authors of the study (YQM and MJQ). Carers received a workbook, which included activities from the book "Skills based caring for a loved one with an eating disorder: The New Maudsley Method" (Treasure et al., 2011). (Spanish version: "Los trastornos de la alimentación: guía práctica para cuidar de un ser querido"; Treasure et al., 2011).

During the sessions, the trained psychologist encouraged discussion about the exercises proposed in the workbook and displayed some of the video-clips from the Digital Versatile Disc (DVD) for carers “How to Care for someone with an Eating Disorder”. The intervention included practical strategies and techniques to help carers develop self-reflective skills and knowledge in order to develop confidence, compassion and the courage to take risks and help their loved one move toward recovery and to look after their own wellbeing by following the “New Maudsley Approach.” Both resources, workbook and online sessions, provide a skills training programme that includes training in stress management, communication (based on motivational interviewing techniques), strategies to reduce accommodation and expressed emotion and to increase extinction training and new habits at home via effective social support. An outline of the content of the ECHO intervention is given in Table 1.

INSERT TABLE 1

As shown in Table 1, the ECHO program has three main components: First, ECHO provides carers with information to strengthen coping with the caregiving role. Second, ECHO teaches carers how to reduce emotionally driven caregiving behaviours, such as high expressed emotion, accommodating and enabling the eating disorder, as well as disagreement and division within the family. Third, ECHO teaches skills of positive communication and behavioural change in order to support recovery (Cardi et al., 2017).

Patients also received a similar intervention that involved eight weekly, individual online sessions delivered by assistant psychologists trained in the Cognitive Maintenance Model of Anorexia Nervosa and the MANTRA protocol and supervised by the principal authors of the study (YQM and MJQ). During the intervention a series

of activities selected for the MANTRA program were taken out. For a more detailed description of the intervention, see Schmidt et al., (2014) and Quiles et al. (2021).

Data Analysis

Independent research assessors, who were unaware of the treatment allocations, conducted pre-randomisation evaluations (baseline: T0), at 2 months (T1) (end of the treatment in ECHO group), at 6 months (T2), at 9 months (T3) and at 12 months (T4).

We used IBM SPSS Statistics 27.0. First, baseline sample characteristics between the ECHO+TAU and TAU group were compared using *t test* for continuous variables and X^2 test for categorical variables. All formal statistical analyses were based on an intent-to-treat principle with all participants analyzed in the condition arm to which they were assigned. Missing data for both groups were imputed using multiple imputation based on fully conditional Markov chain Monte Carlo (Schaefer, 1997). In both groups, it was proved that all the missing data were Missing Completely at Random (MCAR) because the Roderick Little test was not significant in any case. As a result, the final analyses were based on the pooled results of 5 separate imputations.

We conducted general linear models to evaluate the change in outcome variables over all five assessment time points for the ECHO+TAU and TAU group (within factor: time, between factor: ECHO vs. TAU). A significant time x group interaction effect indicates a difference in change between the two cohorts. A significance level of 0.05 was used. Pairwise comparisons were performed following a significant main effect of time (Bonferroni's test).

Effect sizes were calculated using partial eta squared. Partial eta-squared indicates the percentage of variance in the dependent variable attributable to a particular independent variable. A commonly used interpretation is to refer to effect sizes as small

($\eta = 0.2$), medium ($\eta = 0.5$), and large ($\eta = 0.8$) based on benchmarks suggested by Cohen (1988).

Results

Participant characteristics

After screening and baseline assessment, 54 participants were included in the ECHO + TAU group and 54 in TAU. Baseline sociodemographic data and clinical characteristics of their daughters are shown in Table 2. We found no differences between groups in sociodemographic and clinical characteristics measured at baseline.

INSERT TABLE 2

Comparisons between ECHO+TAU and TAU

In Table 3, we present the means, standard deviations, and results of the general linear model analysis, including effect sizes, for the outcomes measured at the five evaluation times for both conditions.

INSERT TABLE 3

The analysis revealed a statistically significant main effect of time in all outcome variables (all p values $\leq .01$) indicating improvements in emotional wellbeing, expressed emotion, caregiving burden, accommodation to illness and care skills in both groups, except for criticism measured with the expressed emotion measure (FQ), the subscale “turning a blind eye” of the illness accommodation scale (AESED), and in the subscales “bigger-picture”, “biting your tongue”, “emotional intelligence” and “frustration-tolerance” of the caregiver skills scale in the TAU group ($p > .05$). Statistically significant time x group interaction effects were observed regarding the Emotional Over-involvement, $F(3.27) = 2.47, p < .05, \eta_p^2 = .02$; emotional wellbeing (with the total score of the DASS-21), $F(3.57) = 3.19, p < .05, \eta_p^2 = .03$; depression, $F(3.40) = 3.27, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .03$; avoidance, $F(3.62) = 3.72, p < .01, \eta_p^2 = .03$;

caregiver skills (total score of the CASK), $F(3.64) = 3.78, p < .01, \eta_p^2 = .03$; as well as self-care and insight acceptance CASK subscales, indicating a greater improvement in these outcomes in ECHO+TAU group compared to TAU.

In figure 2 we present the profile plots (interaction plots) of these relationships. No time x group interaction effects were observed for the other outcome variables (all *p values* > .05).

INSERT FIGURE 2

With regard to effect sizes of the change in outcome variables in the ECHO+TAU group, we found low to medium effects for the expressed emotion (total score of the FQ) and emotional over-involvement subscale. We observed low to medium effects for the caregiving burden (total score of the EDSIS) and two out of the four subscales. We identified low to medium effects for the emotional wellbeing (total score of the DASS-21) and the subscales depression and stress. We also noted low to medium effects for the Illness accommodation (total score of the AESED) and two out of the five subscales. Finally, we observed low to medium effects for the total score of the caregiver skills and the subscale insight-acceptance. Furthermore, medium to large effects were found in the “nutrition impact” subscale of the caregiving burden scale and in the “avoidance” subscale of the illness accommodation measure.

Within the TAU group, we observed low to medium effects for various outcome measures. These included the expressed emotion total score and its emotional over-involvement subscale, the caregiving burden total score and three of its four subscales, the 'stress' subscale of the emotional wellbeing measure, the illness accommodation total score and three of its five subscales, as well as the 'self-care' subscale of the caregiver skills scale. Notably, we did not find any medium to large effects in this

group. In fact, effect sizes tended to be higher in the ECHO+TAU group compared to the TAU group.

Acceptability and feasibility of the intervention

Most of caregivers (81.48%, $n = 44$) completed the ECHO intervention, accomplishing 43.97% of the tasks between sessions and reading the contents of the workbook on 75.29% of occasions. 10 family members did not complete the programme: five carers chose not to finish the intervention voluntarily, two patients required admission to a more intensive resource thus caregivers decided to cease their participation, two caregivers did not complete the intervention due to the patients decided not to participate, and one did not respond to contact attempts. Participant feedback on the intervention is presented in Table 4. As shown in the table, participants indicated a high level of satisfaction with the ECHO.

Discussion

The main aim of the present study was to analyse the effectiveness of adding the ECHO intervention program applied online and individually to the traditional intervention (TAU) for caregivers of patients with ED by means of a RCT. In addition, the second objective was to examine the acceptability and feasibility of this new format of the program ECHO.

The results generally confirmed our first hypothesis, indicating that carers allocated to ECHO+TAU demonstrated significant improvements in expressed emotion, psychological well-being, and lower illness accommodation, and burden in comparison to carers from the control group (TAU). With regard to expressed emotion, as assessed with the FQ, it is interesting to note that only in the ECHO+TAU group was there an

improvement in the factor on 'critical comments', albeit with a small effect size. With regard to the factor 'emotional over-involvement', a significant effect was observed in the interaction, indicating that although changes were observed in the TAU group after treatment, the changes were greater when the ECHO component was added. Previous RCT studies have found no differences in expressed emotion factors (Hodsoll et al., 2017), so one possible explanation could be that the application format (individual and online) has improved the results.

In terms of the impact of ED on caregivers, assessed with the EDSIS, both interventions showed changes, with small to moderate effect sizes, similar to, but smaller than that found in the Adamson's et al. (2019) study. No interaction effect was found for any factor.

Regarding emotional well-being (DASS-21), although statistically significant differences were found for all three factors in both groups, the effect sizes were slightly larger in the group with the addition of ECHO. Effect sizes were larger than in the Adamson's et al., (2019) study. In addition, for the depression factor, an interaction effect was observed, indicating that the ECHO program is more effective in reducing depressive symptomatology in caregivers than using the TAU program alone.

Results on the effect of treatment on caregivers' accommodation to the disease (AESED) showed differences on all factors with slightly larger effect sizes in the ECHO component compared to the TAU group. With the TAU program, significant differences were found in four factors, but not in 'turning a blind eye'. It is interesting to note that the interaction effect is observed in the factor 'avoidance', and only in the ECHO+TAU group was a medium effect size reached. Effect sizes were larger than in the Adamson's et al., (2019) study.

Finally, the greatest differences in the effectiveness of the ECHO program were found in the acquisition of caregiver skills (CASK). In accordance with our second hypothesis, while in the ECHO+TAU group differences were found in all factors, in the TAU group, differences were only found in the factors 'self-care' and 'insight acceptance'. It is precisely these two factors in which an interaction effect is observed, showing that the improvement was significantly greater in the ECHO+TAU group. It is also interesting to note that for factors 'Bigger picture', 'emotional intelligence' and 'frustration tolerance', although with very small effect sizes, differences appeared only at the one-year follow-up. It could indicate that those are aspects that take some time to assimilate. Effect sizes in case of self-care and insight acceptance were close to .40 similar to those found in previous study (Adamson et al., 2019; Hodsoll et al., 2017).

Our third hypothesis was that the efficacy of the combined intervention (ECHO+TAU) would remain stable at the 3-, 6- and 12- month follow-ups. The results confirm this hypothesis for factors that showed improvement. Moreover, it is interesting to note that in most of these factors there is a tendency showing increasing differences from baseline, with significant improvement even between follow-ups ($T_0 > T_1$; $T_1 > T_2$; $T_2 > T_3$; $T_3 > T_4$).

In the present study 81.48% of caregivers completed the ECHO program, showing a higher adherence rate than previous studies (Hodson et al., 2017). This may be due precisely to the fact that in this format the flexibility and ease of attending the sessions was greater, as in this case the sessions were individual and online. However, in the previous studies the formats did not allow for this flexibility as they were group-based and/or through self-help materials (books, DVDs, web-based materials, self-guides) and showed a low adherence of caregivers to the program (Adamson et al., 2019; Hibbs et al., 2015; Hodsoll et al., 2017;). Regarding the 12-month follow-up,

66.66% of the participants completed the evaluation. In previous studies only the 68% of caregivers completed the program in 75% of the sessions, with a 41% data loss 12 months after the end of the program (Hibbs et al., 2015). The study by Adamson et al (2019) increases the percentage of caregivers who did not complete their follow-up assessment three months after the end of ECHO to 48%.

In terms of homework, in the present study, although they indicated that they read the book most of the time (>75%), they only completed 43.97% of the homework assignments. Although they are low rates, those percentages were higher than in previous studies. Hodsoll et al. (2017) highlight that lack of engagement with the intervention may be due to high rates of caregiver distress in the initial phase of adaptation, which, coupled with a lack of time to read the ECHO materials, may explain why only 36% of caregivers in their study reported having read half of the book. In order to improve compliance with these tasks, it would be appropriate to review the content and difficulty of them to ensure that the low compliance rate is not due to the tasks being difficult to understand or perform. In addition, and in order to encourage them to carry out these tasks it might be appropriate to send a "reminder note" to parents to further encourage on the completion of them.

When caregivers were asked about their satisfaction with the program, in 10 of the 12 items the scores were higher than 9 out of 10, and the remaining two were close to 9 (8.77 and 8.80). They rated the program as very satisfactory for improving their experience as caregivers, for developing skills and tools to improve communication with their daughters (more compassionate and less critical), and for dealing with conflictive situations and difficult management of the disorder. Previous research with ECHO (Adamson et al., 2019; Hibbs et al., 2015) have indicated, through qualitative assessments, that caregivers would like more direct guidance in skills training and have

reported that the intervention was helpful. In this sense our study provides a high level of satisfaction with the program and its contents, along with a quantitative assessment of caregivers' satisfaction.

Among the limitations of this study we can highlight the self-administration of the assessment instruments, the reliability of a scale of the EDSIS was below the adequate, and the lack of control over the TAU programs that were being applied in the different hospital units. Another limitation of our study is that we only included female patients with an ED. This prevents us from obtaining relevant data about men. Therefore, in future researches, men should be included in order to know the feasibility and effectiveness of this program in them. In addition, future studies should examine whether the effectiveness of ECHO+TAU on caregivers has implications for patients' improvement in terms of emotional well-being, the quality of the relationship with their caregivers and on the symptoms of the disorder itself.

Among the strengths of this study we highlight that it is a multicenter, randomised, controlled clinical trial, with a longitudinal design comparing two parallel groups, with a relevant size sample. It is the first study that provides evidence on the effectiveness and feasibility of the ECHO program in family members of adolescent patients with an ED. Furthermore, this study shows the effectiveness of a different way of applying this intervention program in the relatives of these patients, since it has been used in individual and online sessions, allowing for individualisation and taking into account in some way the personal circumstances of each family.

The ECHO program for caregivers of patients with EDs was designed to be affordable, scalable and have a broad reach (Cardi et al., 2016). As it has been pointed out in the introduction section, the original ECHO program has worked through formats such as workshops and self-guides, offering caregivers access to program content

through platforms (Treasure et al., 2015). It's important to note the novelty in our trial, where program sessions were individually delivered online to each caregiver. This approach facilitates the immediate and guided transfer of caregiving skills, as previous studies have indicated (Adamson et al., 2019; Ruiz et al., 2023), promoting caregiver program adherence as the schedules of the program sessions were adjusted according to the needs of each caregiver.

The results of this RCT show that after ECHO+TAU and after TAU significant changes in many factors are achieved. However, with the addition of the ECHO program, improvements were achieved in all the factors evaluated, and for the remaining factors where changes were also obtained in the TAU group, the improvement was greater in the case of ECHO+TAU, showing larger interaction effects and/or effect sizes in almost all subscales. Undoubtedly, it is of great importance that family caregivers receive specialised attention adapted to their needs, given that involving the family in the treatment of EDs is a key strategy for their recovery (Treasure & Nazar, 2016). The application of a specific program for caregivers in addition to the TAU achieves positive results in caregivers, which leads to better care for patients with an ED.

In conclusion, this study offers relevant clinical contributions for ED treatment. Results have highlighted that by adding ECHO to TAU, caregivers' skills increase and their emotional state improves. In addition, it has also shown to be effective in reducing some of the negative effects suffered by ED caregivers, such as symptom accommodation, the impact of the disease, expressed emotion, and they feel more competent and able to cope with the care of their loved one. At the clinical level, this study offers an effective, feasible, successful and protocolised program for working with these relatives.

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SUBMITTED

Supplementary material

List of hospitals that participated in the study and the code number of the approvals by the hospital's ethics committees

Eating disorders Unit. Hospital Universitario de San Juan de Alicante. 20/043 Tut.

Eating disorders Unit. Hospital Universitario de la Fe de Valencia.2021-614-1

Eating disorders Unit. Hospital Universitario Reina Sofia de Murcia.2021-30

Day hospital of the CREA center.2020/49555

Day hospital of the ADANER center.2020/49555

SESSION 1	Program presentation and multifactorial origin of the ED: predisposing, precipitating and maintaining factors.
SESSION 2	Description of the Model of Carer Coping.
SESSION 3	Symptom accommodation. Resilience as the transformative ability.
SESSION 4	Description of the Cognitive Interpersonal Maintenance Model of Eating Disorders. Understanding patterns of relationship with the person with the problem through the animal metaphors. How to create distance and provide warmth and guidance.
SESSION 5	Effective communication strategies based on the Motivational Interviewing approach. Listening strategies: basic skills of motivational interviewing such as asking open-ended questions, providing support, reflecting, and summarizing. Communicating with compassion.
SESSION 6	Practice in communication skills.
SESSION 7	Practice in problem-solving and goal-setting skills.
SESSION 8	Review of the content covered during the intervention and practice of the given skills. Relapse prevention.

Table 2. Demographic, psychosocial and clinical variables at baseline.

Carers	Total sample (N=108)	ECHO +TAU Group (N=54)	TAU Group (N=54)	
Gender				
Male	N=16 (15.0%)	N=8 (14.8%)	N=8 (14.8%)	$\chi^2=,01$
Female	N= 91 (85.0%)	N=46 (85.2%)	N=46 (85.2%)	$p=,97$
Age	M= 48.43 (SD=5.26)	M= 49.00 (SD=6.08)	M= 46.00 (SD=6.35)	$t=-1,59$ $p=,11$
Employment status				
Employed	N=78 (72.9%)	N=36 (66.7%)	N=41 (78.8%)	
Unemployed	N=18 (16.8%)	N=11 (20.3%)	N=7 (13.5%)	$\chi^2=3.77$
Job training	N=1 (0.9%)	N=0 (0%)	N=1 (1.9%)	$p=.29$
Other	N=10 (9.3%)	N=7 (13.0%)	N=3 (5.8%)	
Educational status				
First level	N=11 (10.3%)	N=8 (14.8%)	N=3 (5.7%)	
Second level	N=8 (7.5%)	N=4 (7.4%)	N=4 (7.5%)	$\chi^2=9.13$
Third Level	N=4 (3.7%)	N=3 (5.6%)	N=1 (1.9%)	$p=.11$
Vocational training	N=23 (21.5%)	N=6 (11.1%)	N=17 (32.1%)	
University degree	N=58 (54.2%)	N=31 (57.4%)	N=27 (50.9%)	
Other	N=3 (2.8%)	N=2 (3.7%)	N=1 (1.9%)	
Marital status				
Married/Living together	N=81 (75.7%)	N=40 (74.1%)	N=41 (77.4%)	
Divorced/Separated	N=20 (18.7%)	N=11 (20.1%)	N=9 (17.1%)	$\chi^2=1.40$
Single	N=5 (4.7%)	N=2 (3.7%)	N=3 (5.7%)	$p=.71$
Other	N=1 (0.9%)	N=1 (1.9%)	N=0 (0%)	
Relationship with the sufferer				
Mother	N=89 (83.2%)	N=44 (81.5%)	N=45 (84.9%)	
Father	N=15 (14.0%)	N=7 (13.0%)	N=8 (15.1%)	$\chi^2=3.07$
Other	N=3 (2.8%)	N=3 (5.6%)	N=0 (0%)	$p=.22$
Patients				
Age	M=14,95 (SD=1.58)	M=14.00 (SD=1.00)	M=15.00 (SD=0.58)	$t=-.55$ $p=,58$
Diagnosis				
Anorexia Restricting Type	N=73 (68.2%)	N=37 (68.5%)	N=36 (70.6%)	$\chi^2=.47$
Anorexia Purging Type	N=11 (10.3%)	N=5 (9.3%)	N=6 (11.8%)	$p=.93$
Bulimia	N=5 (4.6%)	N=3 (5.6%)	N=2 (3.9%)	
EDNOS	N=16 (15.0%)	N=9 (16.7%)	N=7 (13.7%)	

Illness duration (months)	N=20,65 (SD=18.94)	M=22.00 (SD=3.60)	M=27.00 (SD=7.37)	t=-1.50 p=.14
Care level				
Hospitalization	N=20 (18.7%)	N=8 (14.8%)	N=12 (22.6%)	
Day care	N=57 (53.3%)	N=29 (53.7%)	N=28 (52.8%)	$\chi^2=2.12$
Outpatient	N=30 (28.0%)	N=17 (31.5%)	N=13 (24.5%)	p=.55

Table 3 (I) Results of general linear models analysing outcomes in the ECHO and TAU groups.

	T0 M (SD)	T1 M (SD)	T2 M (SD)	T3 M (SD)	T4 M (SD)	Time	Bonferroni	η_p^2	Time x group
FQ									
ECHO +TAU	28.38(8 .15)	24.98(6 .74)	22.24(6 .37)	23.14(6 .09)	19.93(5.14)	$F(2.72)=$ 21.93; $p<.001$	T0>T1*; T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2**; T1>T4***; T3>T4*	0. 29	$F(3.28)=$ 1.303; $p=0.27$
TAU	29.23(8 .01)	28.58(8 .10)	25.72(7 .67)	25.24(8 .11)	21.70(4.62)	$F(3.72)=$ 15.28; $p<.001$	T0>T2*; T0>T3*; T0>T4***; T1>T2*; T1>T3*; T1>T4**; T2>T4**; T3>T4*	0. 22	
Critical Comments									
ECHO +TAU	10.64(5 .15)	9.86(3. 99)	8.61(3. 35)	10.11(3 .34)	8.56(2 .79)	$F(3.25)=$ 4.96 $p<.01$	T2<T3*; T3>T4*	0. 08	$F(3.72)=$ 0.52; $p=0.70$
TAU	11.20(4 .42)	10.73(5 .01)	10.12(4 .82)	10.46(4 .92)	9.43(2 .50)	$F(3.77)=$ 2.32; $p=0.6$	-	0. 04	
Emotional Over-involvement									
ECHO +TAU	17.74(4 .17)	15.08(3 .79)	13.60(3 .93)	12.91(3 .62)	11.22(3.13)	$F(2.73)=$ 47.20; $p<.001$	T0>T1***;T 0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2*; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 47	$F(3.27)=$ 2.47; $p=0.05$
TAU	18.03(5 .08)	17.84(5 .04)	15.58(4 .31)	14.66(4 .03)	12.67(2.96)	$F(3.48)=$ 25.47; $p<.001$	T0>T2**; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2**; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4**	0. 32	
EDSIS									
ECHO +TAU	36.03(1 3.48)	26.43(1 2.86)	21.35(1 0.86)	20.74(9 .73)	15.30(6.01)	$F(2.92)=$ 47.82 $p<.001$	T0>T1***;T 0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2*; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 47	$F(3.55)=$ 2.14; $p=0.08$

TAU	37.53(1.81)	33.51(4.21)	27.86(2.26)	25.20(0.79)	17.83(7.53)	$F(3.58)=39.41$; $p<.001$	T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2*;T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 42	
Nutrition Impact									
ECHO +TAU	12.11(5.03)	7.46(4.35)	6.03(3.69)	5.45(2.83)	3.48(1.89)	$F(2.81)=63.97$; $p<.001$	T0>T1***;T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2*;T1>T3**; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 54	$F(3.48)=1.19$; $p=0.31$
TAU	13.08(4.33)	10.20(5.17)	7.74(4.66)	7.13(3.85)	4.68(2.62)	$F(3.67)=46.39$; $p<.001$	T0>T1***;T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2*; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 46	
Guilt									
ECHO +TAU	9.90(4.98)	7.73(3.94)	5.78(3.43)	5.93(3.13)	5.41(2.70)	$F(2.79)=21.77$; $p<.001$	T0>T1*;T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2***; T1>T3**; T1>T4***	0. 29	$F(3.48)=1.70$; $p=0.16$
TAU	10.27(5.03)	9.44(4.79)	7.69(3.91)	7.28(3.47)	5.81(2.94)	$F(3.17)=21.34$; $p<.001$	T0>T2**; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2**; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4*	0. 28	
Dysregulated behaviour									
ECHO +TAU	5.51(4.83)	4.61(4.23)	3.54(3.52)	4.30(3.39)	2.85(1.87)	$F(2.76)=8.17$; $p<.001$	T0>T2***;T0>T4**; T3>T4*	0. 13	$F(3.49)=1.20$; $p=0.31$
TAU	5.04(3.19)	5.08(3.77)	4.59(3.82)	4.60(3.05)	3.35(2.60)	$F(3.78)=3.96$; $p<.01$	T0>T4*; T1>T4*	0. 07	
Social Isolation									
ECHO +TAU	8.5(4.8)	6.58(3.73)	5.95(3.67)	5.04(2.36)	3.68(2.05)	$F(2.78)=27.13$; $p<.001$	T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T3**; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 34	$F(3.59)=1.94$; $p=0.11$
TAU	9.13(4.31)	8.79(4.56)	7.73(3.79)	6.52(3.49)	4.17(1.98)	$F(4)=25.09$; $p<.001$	T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T3**; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4*	0. 32	

*: $p < .05$; **: $p < .01$; ***: $p < .001$; AESED: Accomodation to Illness Symptoms Scale; CASK: Caregiver Skills Scale; ECHO: Experienced Carers Helping Others; EDSIS: Eating Disorders Symptom Impact Scale; DASS-21: Depression and Anxiety Stress Scales; FQ: Family Questionnaire; TAU: Treatment as Usual.

Table 3 (II) Results of general linear models analysing outcomes in the ECHO and TAU groups.

	T0 M (SD)	T1 M (SD)	T2 M (SD)	T3 M (SD)	T4 M (SD)	Time	Bonferroni	η_p^2	Time x group
DASS-21									
ECHO +TAU	18.19(1 0.56)	11.25(8 .22)	8.57(6. 35)	9.03(6. 56)	8.68(5. 52)	F(2.46)= 26.62; $p > .001$	T0>T1***; T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2**	0. 33	F(3.57)= 3.19; $p = .02$
TAU	17.73(1 1.37)	16.09(1 2.13)	12.93(1 1.16)	11.97(1 0.74)	9.03(5. 87)	F(3.70)= 10.46; $p < .001$	T0>T2**; T0>T3**; T0>T4***; T1>T4***	0. 16	
Depression									
ECHO +TAU	18.19(1 0.56)	3.86(3. 48)	3.05(2. 64)	3.33(2. 59)	3.13(2. 35)	F(2.24)= 16.65; $p < .001$	T0>T1*; T0>T2**; T0>T3**; T0>T4**	0. 24	F(3.40)= 3.28, $p < .001$
TAU	5.78 (4.30)	5.49(4. 42)	4.44(4. 47)	4.53(4. 06)	3.24(2. 40)	F(3.61)= 60.05; $p < .001$	T0>T4*; T1>T4**	0. 10	
Anxiety									
ECHO +TAU	3.67(3. 65)	2.21(2. 60)	1.56(1. 78)	1.87(2. 15)	1.70(1. 66)	F(2.25)= 10.09; $p < .001$	T0>T4**; T1>T4**	0. 16	F(3.22)= 1.80, $p = .14$
TAU	3.84(3. 73)	3.57(3. 98)	2.69(3. 28)	2.46(3. 16)	1.70(1. 94)	F(3.61)= 44.67; $p < .001$	T0>T1*; T0>T2***; T0>T3*; T0>T4**	0. 10	
Stress									
ECHO +TAU	8.03(3. 64)	5.14(2. 90)	4.21(2. 71)	3.93(2. 58)	3.82(2. 18)	F(3.12)= 33.98; $p < .001$	T0>T1***; T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T4**	0. 39	F(3.81)= 2.22; $p = .07$
TAU	8.15(4. 58)	7.05(4. 59)	5.81(4. 02)	5.02(4. 13)	4.20(2. 52)	F(4)=14. 27; $p < .001$	T0>T2**; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T3*; T1>T4***	0. 21	
AESED									
ECHO +TAU	46.61(2 0.17)	35.27(1 5.28)	28.15(1 4.15)	25.72(1 1.88)	18.80(8 .05)	F(2.68)= 41.84; $p < .001$	T0>T1**; T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2**; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 44	F(3.17)= 0.77; $p = .52$
TAU	49.28(2 1.05)	42.30(2 0.68)	36.22(1 7.61)	32.18(1 4.54)	23.30(1 1.26)	F(3.49)= 29.00; $p < .001$	T0>T2**; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T3**; T1>T4***;	0. 35	

							T2>T4***; T3>T4***		
Avoidance									
ECHO +TAU	17.61(7 .05)	12.09(5 .40)	9.14(5. 00)	8.31(4. 24)	6.15(3. 53)	F(2.94)= 53.91; p<.001	T0>T1***; T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2***; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4*	0. 50	F(3.63)= 3.73; p=.01
TAU	18.30(6 .98)	16.15(7 .28)	13.92(7 .10)	11.97(1 0.74)	7.30(4. 32)	F(4)=37. 12; p<.001	T0>T2**; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T3***; T1>T4***; T2>T4***; T3>T4***	0. 41	
Reassurance seeking									
ECHO +TAU	10.63(7 .40)	7.93(4. 99)	5.79(3. 80)	5.61(3. 33)	4.25(2. 35)	F(2.35)= 22.22; p<.001	T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T2*; T1>T3*; T1>T4***; T2>T4*; T3>T4*	0. 30	F(2.78)= 38.32; p=.94
TAU	11.81(6 .97)	8.95(7. 31)	7.38(5. 87)	7.28(4. 49)	5.56(3. 49)	F(3.01)= 16.68; p<.001	T0>T2***; T0>T3***; T0>T4***; T1>T4**; T3>T4*	0. 24	
Meal ritual									
ECHO +TAU	3.50(4. 06)	3.17(3. 36)	2.73(3. 33)	2.07(1. 97)	1.37(0. 96)	F(2.69)= 6.74; p<.001	T0>T4**; T1>T4**; T2>T4*; T3>T4*	0. 11	F(3.42)= 0.32; p=.81
TAU	4.38(5. 49)	3.91(4. 87)	2.85(2. 95)	2.47(2. 59)	1.81(1. 71)	F(2.67)= 6.54; p<.01	T0>T4**; T1>T4**; T2>T4*	0. 11	

Table 3 (III) Results of general linear models analysing outcomes in the ECHO and TAU groups.

	T0	T1	T2	T3	T4	Time	Bonfer roni	η_p^2	Time x group
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)				
AESED									
Control of Family									
ECHO +TAU	12.69(6. 47)	10.52(4. 84)	8.89(4.1 3)	7.96(3.6 1)	5.84(2.6 6)	F(2.75)= 25.38; p<.001	T0>T2 **; T0>T3 ***, T0>T4 ***, T1>T2 *; T1>T3 **; T1>T4 ***, T2>T4 ***, ;	0. 32	F(3.27)= 0.32; p=.83

								T3>T4	
TAU	13.09(5.43)	11.68(5.53)	10.32(4.42)	9.36(3.84)	7.10(3.32)	F(3.60)=17.71; p<.001	T0>T2 *; T0>T3 **; T0>T4 ***; T1>T3 *; T1>T4 ***; T2>T4 ***; T3>T4 **	0.25	
Turning a blind eye									
ECHO+TAU	2.19(2.93)	1.70(2.26)	1.61(2.29)	1.87(1.61)	1.15(1.07)	F(2.86)=3.20; p=.03	T3>T4 **	0.06	F(3.27)=0.84; p=.87
TAU	2.03(2.83)	1.70(1.66)	1.78(2.29)	1.98(1.96)	1.40(1.33)	F(3.18)=1.23; p=.30	-	0.02	
CASK									
ECHO+TAU	70.98(1.65)	77.32(9.43)	79.47(8.30)	1.87(1.61)	82.15(7.19)	F(3.46)=17.33; p<.001	T0<T1 *; T0<T2 ***; T0<T3 **; T0<T4 ***; T1<T4 **	0.25	F(3.64)=3.79; p=.01
TAU	71.89(1.052)	70.69(1.40)	74.76(1.051)	73.82(1.128)	23.30(1.126)	F(4)=6.69; p<.001	T0<T4 **; T1<T4 **; T3<T4 *	0.11	
Bigger-picture									
ECHO+TAU	75.98(3.27)	79.69(1.047)	80.75(9.20)	80.15(1.00)	83.51(7.66)	F(2.97)=5.38; p<.01	T0<T4 **	0.09	F(3.28)=1.72; p=.16
TAU	77.29(2.61)	76.05(1.195)	78.62(1.203)	77.38(1.177)	79.34(9.40)	F(3.42)=1.22; p=.31	-	0.02	
Self-care									
ECHO+TAU	58.89(8.89)	72.37(3.18)	75.12(1.53)	77.69(0.73)	81.09(8.45)	F(2.25)=31.43; p<.001	T0<T1 ***; T0<T2 ***; T0<T3 ***; T0<T4 ***; T1<T4 ***; T2<T4 ***	0.37	F(3.40)=4.19; p<.01
TAU	59.24(8.08)	60.36(9.59)	66.86(6.07)	69.19(3.84)	77.25(9.79)	F(3.73)=19.99; p<.001	T0<T2 *; T0<T3 **;	0.24	

							T0<T4 ***, ,		
							T1<T3 *, ,		
							T1<T4 ***, ,		
							T2<T4 ***, ,		
							T3<T4 **		
Biting-your-tongue									
ECHO +TAU	70.52(1 6.96)	72.44(1 4.46)	77.17(1 3.90)	72.89(1 5.91)	80.82(1 0.20)	F(4)=6.5 0; p<.001	T0<T4 ***, ,	0. 11	F(4)=1.3 0; p=.27
TAU	69.73(1 6.32)	67.78(1 7.39)	70.37(1 4.42)	71.62(1 2.52)	74.77(1 2.17)	F(3.80)= 2.41; p=.09	- ,	0. 04	
Insight-acceptance									
ECHO +TAU	61.14(1 9.90)	73.51(1 4.05)	77.53(1 1.63)	76.46(1 2.00)	79.58(8. 96)	F(2.68)= 22.28; p<.001	T0<T1 **, ,	0. 30	F(3.42)= 7.82; p<.001
TAU	68.30(1 8.31)	63.94(1 8.48)	69.52(1 7.35)	70.10(1 6.07)	74.31(1 2.88)	F(3.83)= 4.24; p<.01	T0<T2 ***, ,		
							T0<T3 ***, ,		
							T0<T4 ***, ,		
							T1<T4 *		
							T1<T4 **	0. 07	
Emotional Intelligence									
ECHO +TAU	73.81(1 5.77)	78.36(1 2.58)	79.38(1 1.44)	80.75(1 0.13)	81.85(7. 73)	F(3.07)= 5.31; p<.01	T0<T4 **	0. 09	F(3.70)= 1.92; p=.11
TAU	74.01(1 4.95)	72.59(1 5.28)	77.22(1 2.17)	73.92(1 4.17)	78.91(1 0.09)	F(4)=2.9 5; p=.02	- ,	0. 05	
Frustration-tolerance									
ECHO +TAU	76.89(1 3.22)	82.53(9. 36)	82.47(8. 35)	81.27(9. 08)	83.27(7. 01)	F(3.13)= 4.71; p<.01	T0<T4 *	0. 08	F(3.63)= 1.61; p=.18
TAU	75.93(1 2.63)	75.40(1 2.60)	78.91(1 1.63)	76.96(1 3.17)	79.61(8. 55)	F(4)=2.0 9; p=0.8	- ,	0. 04	

Table 4. Carer feedback on the ECHO intervention.

	M(SD)	Range
1. Do you believe the sessions have been helpful in improving your experience as a caregiver?	9.41 (0.88)	7-10
2. Do you believe the sessions have been helpful in...	9.30 (0.82)	7-10
2.1. Better understanding what an eating disorder is?	8.80 (1.32)	6-10
2.2. Better understanding how the eating disorder developed and why it continues to persist?	9.48 (0.82)	7-10
2.3. Having more skills and tools to address your daughter's eating problem?	9.25 (1.10)	5-10
2.4. Improving your communication with your daughter?		

2.5. Using motivational interviewing and active listening strategies in your communication with your daughter?	9.30 (0.88)	7-10
2.6. Having a more compassionate and less critical communication with your daughter regarding the eating disorder?	9.36 (0.89)	7-10
2.7. Having more strategies to handle challenging situations with your daughter, such as mealtime?	9.18 (1.11)	6-10
3. About the intervention...		
3.1. Has it provided you with tools and taught you skills to help your daughter with the eating disorder?	9.25 (0.81)	8-10
	9.60 (0.66)	8-10
3.2. Has it been satisfactory for you?	8.77 (1.38)	5-10
3.3. Was it what you expected?	9.84 (0.37)	9-10
3.4. Would you recommend it to another family member with a daughter with an eating problem?		

Figure 1. CONSORT Diagram Flow.

Figure 2. Profile plots: changes regarding

Overinvolvement (b) Total score DASS-21 (c) depression subscale (d) avoidance subscale, (e) total score CASK, (f) self care subscale and (g) insight subscale

(a) Emotional Overinvolvement

(c) Depression subscale

(d) Avoidance subscale

SUBMITTED

(e) Total score CASK

(f) Self-care subscale

(g) Insight and acceptance subscale

